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Eye-Tracking, Quality Assessment, and QoE Prediction Models for Point Cloud Videos: Extended Analysis of the ComPEQ-MR Dataset

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ABSTRACT Point cloud videos, also termed dynamic point clouds (DPCs), have the potential to provide immersive experiences with six degrees of freedom (6DoF). However, there are still several open issues in understanding the Quality of Experience (QoE) and visual attention of end users while experiencing 6DoF volumetric videos. For instance, the quality impact of compressing DPCs, which requires a significant amount of both time and computational resources, needs further investigation. Also, QoE prediction models for DPCs in 6DoF have rarely been developed due to the lack of visual quality databases. Furthermore, visual attention in 6DoF is hardly explored, which impedes research into more sophisticated approaches for adaptive streaming of DPCs. In this paper, we review and analyze in detail the open-source *Compressed Point cloud dataset with Eye-tracking and Quality assessment in Mixed Reality (ComPEQ-MR)*. The dataset, initially presented in [24], comprises 4 uncompressed (raw) DPCs as well as compressed versions processed by Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) reference tools (*i.e.*, VPCC and 2 GPCC variants). The dataset includes eye-tracking data of 41 study participants watching the raw DPCs with 6DoF, yielding 164 visual attention maps. We analyze this data and present head and gaze movement results here. The dataset also includes results from subjective tests conducted to assess the quality of the DPCs, each both uncompressed and compressed with 12 levels of distortion, resulting in 2132 quality scores. This work presents the QoE performance results of the compression techniques, the factors with significant impact on participant ratings, and the correlation of the objective Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) metrics with Mean Opinion Scores (MOS). The results indicate superior performance of the VPCC codec as well as significant variations in quality ratings based on codec choice, bitrate, and quality/distortion level, providing insights for optimizing point cloud video compression in MR applications. Finally, making use of the subjective scores, we trained and evaluated models for QoE prediction for DPCs compressed using the pertinent MPEG tools. We present the models and their prediction results, noting that the fine-tuned ITU-T P.1203 models exhibit good correlation with the subjective ratings. The dataset is available at <https://ftp.itec.aau.at/datasets/ComPEQ-MR/>.

INDEX TERMS dynamic point clouds, eye-tracking data, visual attention maps, subjective study, quality of experience, QoE prediction models, machine learning, mixed reality

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the advent of Extended Reality (XR) technologies, including Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR), has significantly transformed user interaction with digital content, leading to a growing demand for high quality of experience (QoE). Dynamic point clouds (DPCs) play a critical role in this transformation due to their

ability to provide a rich representation of 3D environments and objects [13]. In contrast to traditional 2D video formats, DPCs enable immersive experiences through six degrees of freedom (6DoF) interactions, allowing end users to navigate through and interact with near-lifelike content. A point cloud (PC) can include several millions of points, each of which comprises geometry information (*i.e.*, x,y,z coordinates of

the point) and/or attributes (*i.e.*, RGB colors). This leads to gigabits of data for an uncompressed 1-second DPC with 30 frames per second.

Recent advances in MR applications and devices—such as Microsoft HoloLens 2¹ and Apple Vision Pro²—have accelerated the use of DPCs across domains, including education (*e.g.*, simulated clinical scenarios [18]), gaming [35], autonomous driving [12], and telepresence (*e.g.*, video conferencing [33]). However, delivering DPCs is challenging due to their substantial bandwidth requirements. A promising approach combines point cloud compression (PCC) [30] with HTTP adaptive streaming (HAS) [4]. Compression reduces the bitrate of both geometry and attribute data by removing redundancy, quantizing the data, and employing hierarchical structures, although at the cost of some visual quality. HAS adapts to fluctuating network conditions by selecting appropriate encoded representations to minimize rebuffering events while maximizing perceived quality.

It is of importance to understand the impacts of DPC compression on the QoE when assessing the performance of DPC compression approaches and deciding on a suitable compressed DPC to deliver to end users based on certain conditions, such as network bandwidth and device rendering ability. A subjective test study is a common way to reveal insights about these impacts. DPCs have been tested under different environments, including 2D screens [32], [37], VR head-mounted displays (HMDs) [31], [48], and MR HMDs [22], [23]. In these works, the participants were asked to watch various compressed DPCs and rate their qualities. The average rating scores were used for the mean opinion scores (MOS) on those DPCs. Besides, eye-tracking data were collected through the HMDs in other works [3], [46], which can support the selection of multimedia quality [16] and better understand the QoE of end users streaming DPCs. However, an in-depth analysis of eye-tracking and QoE assessment for DPCs in an MR condition, where DPCs appear in a physical environment and end users can move freely and interact with DPCs (with 6DoF), is still limited.

In this paper, we revisit a study that created an open source dataset called *ComPEQ-MR* (*Compressed Point cloud dataset with Eye-tracking and Quality assessment in Mixed Reality*), initially presented in [24]. We provide an in-depth analysis of this dataset to gain insights on visual attention and on the QoE of end users of DPCs in an MR environment. The dataset comprises 4 DPCs, each both uncompressed and compressed with 12 levels of distortion. The DPCs were processed by Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) reference tools (*i.e.*, *Video-based PCC* (VPCC) and 2 variants of *Geometry-based PCC* (GPCC)). The dataset includes 164 visual attention maps, acquired from 41 study participants watching the uncompressed DPCs. In a subjective QoE study, the 41 participants assessed the quality of the DPCs at different quality levels and thus created 2132 opinion scores. The QoE performance results

for the DPC codecs and the major factors influencing the QoE ratings are presented. Finally, making use of the opinion scores, we trained and evaluated QoE prediction models.

The main contributions of this paper are therefore:

- *Eye-tracking data*: It presents and analyzes eye-tracking data of participants watching several DPCs with 6DoF. This data allows for the examination of visual attention and saliency, enhancing the understanding of user interactions with DPCs in MR environments.
- *Quality assessment*: It presents the quality results of a subjective study of uncompressed and compressed DPCs from a modern dataset in an MR setting, allowing the study participants to interact with (*i.e.*, move around) the presented DPCs with 6DoF.
- *Comparative analysis*: It indicates superior QoE performance of VPCC compression and identifies the factors with significant impact on the participants' QoE ratings: codec choice and quality/distortion level.
- *MOS vs. objective metrics*: It further analyzes the relationship between bitrate and the correlation of the PSNR metrics with the subjective scores (MOS), contributing to a better understanding of quality metrics in the context of DPCs.
- *QoE prediction models*: It introduces both heuristics and machine learning-based models for predicting the QoE of end users while watching DPCs in an MR environment.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of related work on point cloud compression, eye-tracking experiments, subjective quality tests for DPCs, and models for QoE prediction. Section III details the ComPEQ-MR dataset and the methodology used for data collection. Section IV contains an analysis of the eye-tracking data, followed by a discussion of the subjective study results in Section V. Our proposed QoE prediction models and their evaluation are presented in Section VI. Finally, Section VII concludes this paper.

II. RELATED WORK

A. POINT CLOUD COMPRESSION

Point cloud compression (PCC) has received significant interest in academic research [28], [44]. The Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) has been developing two technologies: (1) *Geometry-based PCC* (GPCC) and (2) *Video-based PCC* (VPCC) [2]. GPCC encodes the 3D coordinates of PCs directly to create a compressed format, utilizing methods like Octree or Trisoup (triangle soup). The color information of a PC can be encoded by the Region Adaptive Hierarchical Transform (RAHT) or the Predicting/Lifting (Predlift) transform. In contrast, VPCC takes a more indirect route by projecting the 3D points onto 2D images and then employing traditional encoders, such as HEVC, to compress these images. This approach allows VPCC to utilize existing efficient coding techniques and facilitates easier deployment.

There have also been several novel PCC approaches from researchers. Zhang [44] introduced a learning-based method

¹<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/hololens/hololens2-hardware>.

Accessed 27 August 2025.

²<https://www.apple.com/uk/apple-vision-pro/>. Accessed 27 August 2025.

for lossy compression called DeepPCC. DeepPCC employs stacked neural network layers to jointly represent the geometry and attribute information of PCs. Similarly, the works in [20], [43] attempted to combine geometry compression and attribute compression into a joint solution. However, the authors have not published their source code for testing at the time of our work. Thus, we did not consider these PCC approaches in this paper.

B. EYE-TRACKING DATA

Visual saliency is widely leveraged for perception-aware optimization across coding, transport, and rendering. Saliency models are typically validated against ground-truth fixations collected via eye tracking [17], where a fixation denotes maintaining gaze on a single location for a defined interval [1]. A public dataset that combines mean opinion scores (MOS) with eye-tracking data is essential for advancing efficient techniques for coding, transmission, and rendering of DPCs.

Zhang *et al.* [45] introduced an experimental methodology to obtain reliable eye-tracking data for image quality assessment, while David *et al.* [8] captured head and eye movements in free-viewing experiment of 360° videos and released saliency maps, scanpaths, and users behaviors statistics. For volumetric media, Alexiou *et al.* [3] conducted VR eye-tracking on static PCs for saliency modeling. Zhou *et al.* [46] collected gaze heat maps for DPCs viewed with an HMD and analyzed how quality distortions affect gaze. Nevertheless, the distorted DPCs are not publicly available.

Recent studies further extend saliency-guided quality assessment and gaze prediction in 360°/VR and volumetric content using deep learning and transformer-based models, introduce larger-scale datasets, and begin exploring AR/MR interaction effects on attention [36], [40], [42]. To the best of our knowledge, an eye-tracking dataset for DPCs in an MR environment has not yet been reported.

C. SUBJECTIVE QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Many works have focused on subjective quality assessment for PCs.

Ak *et al.* [2] conducted a comprehensive subjective evaluation of static point clouds, involving more than 1200 stimuli (*i.e.*, test sequences) and more than 3000 participants. However, since all assessments were performed on 2D monitors, viewers had no means to interact with the 3D content, and the study did not incorporate any eye-tracking measurements. Zhou *et al.* [47] and Subramanyam *et al.* [29] concentrated on subjective studies of DPCs for VR environments rather than MR; GPCC was partially excluded from these analyses.

Zhou *et al.* [46] presented a dataset for assessing the subjective and objective quality of DPCs. Though this work includes qualitative insights from participant interviews, highlighting factors influencing perceptual quality and user behavior, it considered VR environments rather than MR. The compressed DPCs were not made available. Fan *et al.* [10] conducted subjective quality assessment of point clouds in AR

environments, including DPCs; only VPCC was taken into account. Christensen *et al.* [7] compared VPCC, a GPCC variant, and Draco³ on various datasets, some of them containing DPCs. A relevant result was that VPCC clearly outperforms the other codecs in terms of the reconstruction quality of dense DPCs, but performs worse on sparse point clouds.

Weil *et al.* [37] performed a subjective user study using two DPCs at different frame rates and viewing distances as well as the VPCC and Draco codecs at various quantization levels. Both codecs can provide high-quality presentations, yet Draco at a significantly higher bitrate. It was found that higher bitrate does not necessarily imply higher quality ratings.

Our previous work [22], [23] considered the impact of quality levels, quality switches, viewing distance, and content characteristics on the QoE for PCs in AR environments through a subjective study. Subjective tests were performed with the distorted PCs compressed by VPCC and watched on an AR HMD. However, the participants were asked to stand still; thus, there was no interaction.

Unlike these related works, we provide opinion scores and eye-tracking data collected in interactive subjective tests in an AR environment. Our subjective data can benefit the validation of QoE prediction models, objective quality metrics development, and help researchers understand the visual attention of participants. We also publish the quality distortions of PCs for reproducibility.

D. OBJECTIVE QOE MODELS

In the field of objective point cloud quality assessment (PCQA), various no-reference (NR) techniques have been developed [26]. These techniques aim to estimate the QoE of the PCs without relying on another PC to refer to, *i.e.*, by utilizing the features of the PC itself. Machine learning (ML)-based models fall into this category.

Weil *et al.* [37] trained supervised ML models to predict the QoE score with the data obtained from their subjective test. However, the DPCs were displayed in 2D screens, and MR HMDs were not considered in their test. Furthermore, they only utilized the VPCC and Draco codecs for point cloud compression.

The work by Nguyen *et al.* [22] evaluated ML models in a similar way, but on a subjective testing dataset that considered the impact of quality levels, quality switches, viewing distance, and content characteristics on the QoE for DPCs in AR [23]. Only the VPCC codec was utilized, but the point clouds were shown to the users via an MR headset.

Another work by Nguyen *et al.* [21] evaluated the mode 0 of the ITU-T P.1203 model [27], fine-tuned on point cloud metadata from the same study. This objective metric utilized the metadata a PC video shares in common with 2D videos to predict the QoE.

³<https://github.com/google/draco>

FIGURE 1: Platform architecture used to conduct tests and collect data.

III. COMPEQ-MR POINT CLOUD DATASET

The study described in [24] comprised two tasks: eye-tracking testing and subjective quality assessment. While Sections IV and V discuss expanded results obtained from the findings made in the ComPEQ-MR dataset, this section provides an overview of the dataset collected in the ComPEQ-MR study and recaps the testing methodology used.

A. PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

Conducting the tests and collecting the data was made possible using our subjective testing platform, the architecture of which is depicted in Figure 1. The platform is built using Unity⁴ and was run on a Windows 10 workstation with an Intel i7-12700H CPU, 32 GB of DDR5-4800 MHz RAM, and an NVIDIA RTX A2000 GPU. The workstation performed the computations and stored the data, while the Microsoft HoloLens 2 was used as the interface device with the participant. Interfacing with the HoloLens 2 was made possible by the use of the Mixed Reality Toolkit (MRTK) ²5 software development kit from Microsoft. More information about the platform can be found in a publication accepted to EuroXR '25 [34].

B. PARTICIPANTS

41 persons participated in this study [24], including 19 (46%) females and 22 (54%) males. 18 (45%) persons were in the age group of 18 to 24 years, 14 (35%) were between 25 and 34, 7 (17.5%) between 35 and 44, and 1 (2.5%) between 55 and 64. 17 persons (41.5%) had never used an AR headset before, 16 (39%) fewer than 5 times, 7 (17%) between 5 and 20 times, and 1 (2.5%) person was a frequent user (more than 20 times). Most of the participants were students or staff of the University of Klagenfurt. All of them passed the Ishihara color vision test [5] before the experiment.

Using a questionnaire, the participants were asked about demographic data (as partially summarized above), their feelings of immersion in the MR scenes, and potential symptoms of AR sickness (before and after the test).

C. POINT CLOUD VIDEO SEQUENCES

The state-of-the-art uncompressed, voxelized, 10-bit point cloud dataset UVG-VPC [11] was deployed. This dataset

⁴Version 2021.3.19f1. <https://unity.com/>. Accessed: 04 September 2025.

⁵<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/mrtk-unity/mrtk2/?view=mrtkunity-2022-05>. Accessed 04 September 2025.

TABLE 1: UVG-VPC sequences [11] used in the ComPEQ-MR dataset. Red and green numbers indicate that the sequence has low and high values, respectively, for corresponding metrics.

Name	Description	Snapshot
BlueSpin	A person wearing a blue t-shirt and spinning at a consistent rate. SI: 20.8 TI: 8.0 Colorfulness: 8.6	
CasualSquat	A person wearing a striped shirt and jeans in the performance of a squat exercise. SI: 53.5 TI: 19.0 Colorfulness: 11.5	
FlowerDance	A person in a long, flowing dress spinning and twirling. SI: 43.9 TI: 22.3 Colorfulness: 25.3	
ReadyForWinter	A person donning a beanie and scarf. SI: 20.6 TI: 11.5 Colorfulness: 7.8	

TABLE 2: Encoder parameters to generate compressed DPCs.

Compression		Quality Levels				
		r01	r02	r03	r04	r05
VPCC	Geometry QP	36	32	28	20	16
	Texture QP	47	42	37	27	22
GPCC-Oct-Pred	QP	-	-	40	34	28
	Depth	-	-	0.5	0.75	0.875
GPCC-Tri-RAHT	QP	40	34	28	22	-
	Level	5	4	3	2	-

comprises 12 video sequences of humans with various content characteristics, captured at a frame rate of 25 fps, each 10 s long. Four DPCs, as seen in Table 1, were selected that have large differences in the criteria *spatial information* (SI), *temporal information* (TI), and *colorfulness* (CF) to cover a wide diversity: *BlueSpin*, *CasualSquat*, *FlowerDance*, and

TABLE 3: Bitrates of the compressed DPCs in Mbit/s.

Point Cloud	Raw	VPCC					GPCC-Oct-Pred			GPCC-Tri-RAHT			
	vox10	r01	r02	r03	r04	r05	r03	r04	r05	r01	r02	r03	r04
BlueSpin	924.81	1.43	1.88	2.60	6.17	10.34	1.37	4.61	10.99	0.99	2.17	4.87	10.98
CasualSquat	829.47	2.05	3.21	5.46	15.98	25.49	1.79	8.04	23.66	3.83	9.26	19.71	38.78
FlowerDance	1019.65	2.18	3.47	5.84	18.69	32.24	1.98	8.64	25.09	3.03	8.02	19.09	39.91
ReadyForWinter	1072.33	1.62	2.12	2.96	7.65	13.59	1.56	5.29	13.42	1.00	2.29	6.00	14.24

ReadyForWinter.

These DPCs were compressed using MPEG’s reference software tools for VPCC and GPCC point cloud compression, the latter deploying the specific tool combinations *GPCC-Oct-Pred* (*Octree* and *Predlift* modes) and *GPCC-Tri-RAHT* (*Trisoup* and *RAHT* modes) to process the point clouds. Using different quantization and other parameter configurations (Table 2), the sequences were compressed into 12 different distortion levels: 5 quality levels for VPCC ($r01 \dots r05$), 3 for GPCC-Oct-Pred ($r03 \dots r05$), and 4 for GPCC-Tri-RAHT ($r01 \dots r04$). Thus, together with the uncompressed version, 13 quality levels per DPC are contained in the ComPEQ-MR dataset, leading to a total of 52 DPC sequences. The bitrates of the 13 representations are shown in Table 3.

D. EYE-TRACKING DATA

Before the study began, the built-in eye calibration⁶ of the HoloLens 2 was performed for each participant, since the eye-tracking services of the HoloLens do not function without calibration. This actual eye-tracking task consisted of two subtasks: (i) error measurement and (ii) watching the PC videos.

The second subtask consisted of the participants watching 20 s long uncompressed (voxelized 10-bit format) PC sequences of the four DPCs mentioned in Subsection III-C. The participants were allowed to move freely in the space of the test room (6DoF within a 4 m × 4 m area), but were required to return to the starting point before starting the next sequence. The participant’s gaze origin and gaze direction were stored once per DPC frame. The order of the DPCs was randomized among the participants to avoid bias. The subtasks were alternated until the participant had watched all four sequences.

The data obtained from this task were processed to generate fixation heatmaps for the DPCs. Figure 2 shows the fixation heatmap of a frame of the BlueSpin object from four views.

The heatmap images for every frame, along with fixation weights for each point of the frames for all four PCs, were made available in the ComPEQ-MR dataset⁷.

FIGURE 2: Fixation heatmap of a BlueSpin frame in four views.

E. QUALITY RATINGS

Following eye-tracking tests, participants in the subjective study rated their QoE for DPCs presented via the Microsoft HoloLens 2. Each subject viewed 52 DPCs, as described in Subsection III-C, each lasting 20 s, in randomized order. They began viewing a DPC (a character) from 2 m away and could then move freely within a 4 m × 4 m area. After each DPC presentation, participants entered their QoE score using a user-friendly HoloLens 2 interface, returned to the initial position, and proceeded to the next DPC. The study employed the single-stimulus Absolute Category Rating (ACR) methodology with a 5-level Likert scale (5–excellent to 1–bad) and adhered to relevant ITU recommendations as outlined in [24]. Each session lasted approximately 30 min.

The subjective QoE study yielded 2132 opinion scores (4 DPCs, 13 quality levels (1 raw/uncompressed, 12 distorted versions), 41 participants). The rating scores for each DPC are available in the ComPEQ-MR dataset. The results are presented in Section V.

IV. EYE-TRACKING RESULTS

From the eye-tracking study described in Subsection III-D, we collected participants’ gaze data in the form of their gaze origin and gaze direction for every frame. This data was utilized to compile visual fixation heatmaps for the participants, as described in [24]. We analyzed this data further to obtain more insight into the overall behavior of the participants with regard to head and gaze movement. This section discusses

⁶<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/design/eye-tracking>. Accessed 27 August 2025.
⁷<https://ftp.itec.aau.at/datasets/ComPEQ-MR/>. Accessed 27 August 2025.

selected results from this analysis. The code for this analysis, along with more results not discussed here, can be found on GitHub⁸.

A. GAZE DATA OVERVIEW

Unity records the gaze origin and gaze direction as a set of x , y , and z values for every frame using the MRTK 2 library. The gaze origin is a 3-dimensional vector representing the participant's position offset from the scene origin in meters, as measured by Unity. The scene origin in our case was the point on the floor directly below the participant when they started the eye-tracking task. The gaze direction is represented as a 3-dimensional unit vector in degrees.

Since we allowed the participants to have six degrees of freedom during the tests, a change in the gaze origin can be brought about by either the participants moving their head in any way (tilting, shaking, or rolling) or by them moving their whole body (or just the head) to a new location. From now on, we will refer to the change in the gaze origin as *head movement*. A change in the gaze direction, referred to as *gaze movement*, results from the participants moving their irises, with or without moving their heads.

B. PREPROCESSING GAZE DATA

It must be noted that, unlike processing the eye-tracking data to generate fixation maps [24], no pre-processing for accuracy is needed in this case since we only concern ourselves with the difference between a participant's gaze on a frame-to-frame basis, and removing the average angular error every frame would not impact these results.

The first 1.5 s were discarded to account for possibly erratic initial movements. After extracting the head movement and gaze movement change per frame, and consequently per second, the gaze data was filtered using the interquartile range (IQR) method [38] per participant per point cloud. After filtering, we were left with 2857 data points of gaze and head movement per second.

C. ANALYZING HEAD AND GAZE MOVEMENT

The analysis of the filtered data yielded the following results. The average head movement per participant was found to be 0.478 m/s, with a standard deviation of 0.385 m/s. The average gaze movement per participant was 65.728 °/s with a standard deviation of 57.381 °/s.

We classified the participants into three movement categories based on these movement velocities. Participants in the lowest and the highest 25 percentiles based on the respective velocity were placed in the *Low* and *High* categories, respectively, while the rest were placed in the *Medium* category.

The thresholds obtained for low and high head movement were determined to be 0.368 m/s and 0.630 m/s, respectively. Similarly, the thresholds for low and high gaze movements were set at 47.682 °/s and 85.913 °/s, respectively.

⁸<https://github.com/shivivats/PointCloudDataAnalysis>. Accessed 28 August 2025.

FIGURE 3: Average head vs. gaze movement velocities per participant for each movement category and overall for point clouds.

Interestingly, based on these thresholds, the same number of participants were classified into the three categories for both movement types. Namely, 11, 19, and 11 participants were classified into the *Low*, *Medium*, and *High* categories, respectively. However, only some participants belong to the same category for both movements. More specifically, only

- 4 out of 11 low head movement participants also have low gaze movement,
- 8 out of 19 medium head movement participants also have medium gaze movement, and
- 7 out of 11 high head movement participants also have high gaze movement.

Figure 3 shows the average head and gaze movements of the participants in the three head movement categories across all videos, represented by the colored dots. The figure also contains the head and gaze movement per point cloud, averaged across all participants. These values, represented by the red symbols, are as follows:

- *CasualSquat*: 0.542 m/s and 76.9 °/s
- *FlowerDance*: 0.478 m/s and 64.2 °/s
- *BlueSpin*: 0.450 m/s and 64.5 °/s
- *ReadyForWinter*: 0.445 m/s and 57.6 °/s

CasualSquat is the DPC with the highest movement in both categories, which can be attributed to its DPC sequence having the most movement due to the squatting motion. Similarly, the *ReadyForWinter* object has the least movement in both categories since the sequence is simply a person tying and untying a scarf around their neck.

D. HEAD AND GAZE MOVEMENT OVER TIME

Figure 4 depicts the head and gaze movement over time for the *CasualSquat* and *ReadyForWinter* point clouds. The points on the graph represent the movement averaged over all

FIGURE 4: Head and gaze movement over time per point cloud for *CasualSquat* and *ReadyForWinter*.

participants for the previous one second. These DPC objects were chosen as they represent the most and least amount of movement, as discussed in the previous subsection. The difference in the participants' behavior is evident in the graphs, where the participants are shown to have more movement for the *CasualSquat* object almost the whole time they are watching the DPC sequences.

V. SUBJECTIVE STUDY RESULTS

Basic results of the ComPEQ-MR subjective study were already described in our previous paper [24]. To make the current paper largely self-contained, that information is briefly recapped in the first two subsections. The remainder of the section presents advanced results and discussions of the subjective study.

A. OPINION SCORES

The raw opinion scores of the participants for all tested DPCs are shown in Figure 5. Some video sequences receive consistent scores from all participants. For example, the 18th and 41st videos (*i.e.*, *BlueSpin* and *CasualSquat* encoded by GPCC-Tri-RAHT at quality *r01*, respectively) have mostly all low scores (*i.e.*, scores 1 or 2), while the 5th video gets high scores (*i.e.*, scores 4 and 5) from most of the participants. Regarding the participants, some of them are not satisfied with the quality of the video sequences (*e.g.*, participants 2 and 30), while others feel the opposite (*e.g.*, participant 17).

Mean Opinion Scores (MOS) were calculated according to ITU-R BT.500-15 [15]. 95% confidence intervals (CI) were also computed. In the subjective tests, no outliers were detected.

B. QOE PERFORMANCE OF THE COMPRESSION ALGORITHMS

Figure 6 compares the basic QoE (rate–MOS) performance of the compression algorithms (codecs) used in the study. When using – for the sake of fair comparison – the number of *bits per point* (bpp) for the rate metric, VPCC clearly achieves the best QoE (MOS) results, in accordance with findings of

FIGURE 5: Raw opinion scores

related work [2]. GPCC-Oct-Pred provides lower MOS than GPCC-Tri-RAHT, which is opposite to [2].

C. IMPACT FACTORS

First, we study 3 factors that may have a statistically significant impact on the quality ratings of the participants: compression algorithm (codec), encoding quality (quality level), and DPC content (characteristics). We utilize the three-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test to determine the potential impact. The ANOVA results show that *codec* and *quality level* as well as the interaction between these two factors have a statistically significant effect ($p < 0.001$) on the ratings of participants. On the contrary, content and other interactions involving the content do *not* significantly contribute to explaining the variance in the ratings ($p > 0.05$).

1) Impact of Quality Level

Figure 7 shows the quality ratings for various quality levels and codecs, including the raw content version. Generally, a higher quality level achieves better scores, regardless of the codecs and video content; and the raw/uncompressed DPCs always get the highest scores, close to 5. For the VPCC codec (Figure 7a), for example, the DPCs encoded at quality level

FIGURE 6: Bits per point vs. MOS for each video. The error bar is the 95% CI.

FIGURE 7: Quality ratings. Green triangles \blacktriangle are average ratings.

$r01$ are rated on average less than 2 out of 5, that means a *poor* visual quality, whereas quality $r05$ can achieve up to 3.8, close to a *good* score.

Post-hoc pairwise, Tukey's HSD test (Honestly Significant Difference) reveals that quality ratings do *not* differ significantly ($p > 0.05$) between:

- For VPCC: (i) $r04$ and $r05$ for all contents, (ii) $r02$ and $r03$ for *CasualSquat*, (iii) $r03$ and $r04$ for *FlowerDance*, (iv) $r01$ and $r02$ for *ReadyForWinter*.
- For GPCC-Oct-Pred: $r03$ and $r04$ for *BlueSpin*.
- For GPCC-Tri-RAHT: $r03$ and $r04$ for *BlueSpin*, *CasualSquat*, and *FlowerDance*.

These findings are similar to [37] and indicate that, in specific cases, DPCs can be encoded into lower quality levels (with lower bitrates) to conserve bandwidth during transmission, without significantly compromising on the user's QoE.

2) Impact of Point Cloud Codec

As mentioned, there are significant differences in quality ratings across the codecs (VPCC, GPCC-Oct-Pred, and GPCC-Tri-RAHT). To further explore these discrepancies, a post-hoc analysis using Tukey's HSD test was performed. This

FIGURE 8: MOS vs. bitrate.

FIGURE 9: PSNR vs. MOS.

analysis confirmed that the quality ratings for all pairs of encoders were significantly different from each other ($p < 0.05$). These findings imply that the choice of encoder has a notable impact on the quality ratings.

3) Impact of Prior Usage of an AR Headset

As indicated in Subsection III-B, there is quite some diversity in the participants' prior experience (or, frequency) of AR headset usage. Thus, ANOVA analysis and Tukey's HSD tests were performed as well. The results initially showed that this factor does have a statistically significant impact on the quality ratings. However, the single frequent AR headset user ("more than 20 times") turned out to have rated differently. After removing them from the analyses, the results indicate that the prior usage frequency of an AR headset does *not* have a statistically significant impact on the quality ratings.

D. FURTHER ANALYSES OF THE QOE RESULTS

1) MOS vs. Bitrate

Figure 8 shows the relationship between bitrate and MOS for the three codecs. The curves are fitted using a logarithmic function.

MOS and bitrate correlate with each other well, except in cases of unusually high bitrates, as seen in Figures 8a and 8c. This suggests that an increase in bitrate beyond a certain threshold does not lead to a corresponding improvement in perceived quality, confirming the finding at the end of Subsection V-C1.

2) MOS vs. PSNR

PSNR metrics for the DPCs were computed using the *MPEG-pcc-dmetric* tool [19]. Figure 9 shows that higher PSNR values correspond with higher MOS, as would be expected.

FIGURE 10: Correlation coefficients for MOS vs. PSNR.

However, interesting conclusions can be derived from Figure 10, which shows the Spearman and Pearson correlation coefficients of color PSNR (cPSNR) and geometry PSNR (gPSNR) with MOS for all three codecs.

The correlation between cPSNR and MOS is significantly lower than the correlation between gPSNR and MOS, for both correlation coefficients. This suggests that, even though there is a general trend for the MOS values to increase as cPSNR increases, such an increase is not always guaranteed or proportional.

E. PARTICIPANTS' FEELINGS OF IMMERSION AND AR SICKNESS SYMPTOMS

In the post-test questionnaire, the participants were asked: "How would you describe the general experience?", with the additional explanation whether or not they would agree to the following assertion: "I felt the objects were part of the real environment." Figure 11 shows that 13 persons (strongly) disagree with that assertion, *i.e.*, do not feel that the MR scenes are immersive, 11 are neutral, whereas 17 participants (strongly) agree. Thus, although the DPCs presented were partially of good to excellent quality, the immersiveness of the MR presentations has quite some room for improvement.

The participants were also asked to report about potential AR sickness symptoms. Based on a recent questionnaire developed in [14], the participants provided their assessments on 9 AR sickness symptoms before and after the test (general discomfort, fatigue, headache, eye strain, fullness of the head, dizziness (eyes open), dizziness (eyes closed), vertigo, and nausea) on a 4-point Likert scale [0–none; 1–slight; 2–moderate; 3–severe]. Figure 12 depicts the results. In general, quite some symptoms emerged or were intensified by the test, yet mostly by only 1 level, if at all. Eye strain turned out to be the most common symptom. With one exception (a severe condition), the reported symptoms were mostly slight, with a few moderate post-test conditions. The results indicate that the participants could well manage the test with the HoloLens 2 headset.

We define the test's effect on the participants as the difference in the levels of AR sickness symptoms reported after

FIGURE 11: Feelings of immersion: (dis-)agreement with the assertion that "objects were part of the real environment."

FIGURE 12: AR sickness symptoms before and after the test.

and before the test, *i.e.*, post-test condition minus pre-test condition, for all 9 symptoms. To investigate whether the test's effect had a significant impact on the quality ratings, we split the participants into 3 groups: group 1 did not report any differences in symptoms (*no effect*, 18 participants); group 2 includes participants who reported that 1–4 conditions worsened by 1 level (*slight effect*, 12 participants); group 3 includes 1 person who reported that 8 conditions worsened by 1 level, and 10 persons who reported that at least 1 condition worsened by 2 levels (*moderate to severe effect*, 11 participants). (There were rare cases where a post-test condition was reported better than the pre-test condition; see Figure 12. These cases were counted as *no* differences in the analyses.)

ANOVA analysis and Tukey's HSD tests were performed. The results indicate that the group 2 ratings significantly differed from the other groups' ratings. However, the group 1 ratings (*no effect* group) and the group 3 ratings (*moderate to severe effect* group) did not significantly differ from each other. Thus, the potential hypothesis that the test's effect significantly impacted the quality ratings can be rejected.

VI. TRAINING AND EVALUATION OF QOE PREDICTION MODELS

Previous studies [37], including our former work [22], have found that machine learning (ML) models can be effective in predicting the QoE of DPCs. Similar to our previous work, we have trained ML models on the ComPEQ-MR dataset, and we evaluate their performance here. Furthermore, we have also fine-tuned the Mode 0 of the P.1203 model [27] from ITU-T using the ComPEQ-MR dataset. We consider both approaches to objective QoE prediction and present the results in this section. The Python code for these analyses and the detailed results can be found here: <https://github.com/shivivats/PointCloudDataAnalysis>.

A. MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

1) Data Preparation

As described earlier, we presented the subjective test participants with 52 DPC sequences, obtained from 4 PC objects and encoded using VPCC, GPCC-Oct-Pred, and GPCC-Tri-RAHT. After initial testing, we discovered that training one model for the three codecs would not be viable due to the differences in the encoding parameters used for each codec. Additionally, we learned that combining the ComPEQ-MR dataset with our first dataset [22] would not lead to viable results due to the different natures of the parameters used during both subjective testing rounds.

Thus, we decided to use only the ComPEQ-MR dataset and train ML models separately for each codec using the content characteristics and specific encoding parameters.

The former can be represented by the bitrates of the encoded bitstreams of the DPC sequences. The latter can be represented by the quantization parameters (QPs) utilized by each codec. These are as follows (see also Table 2):

- VPCC: Geometry QP (G-QP) and Texture QP (T-QP);
- GPCC-Oct-Pred: QP and Depth;
- GPCC-Tri-RAHT: QP and Level.

From the 2132 data points we obtained, we removed the ones where the participants were watching the raw (uncompressed) sequences, as these did not have any quantization parameters associated with them and thus could not be used to train the models. We separated the remaining 1968 responses by codec and removed outliers using the interquartile range (IQR) method [38]. After filtering, we were left with 776, 464, and 622 data points for VPCC, GPCC-Oct-Pred, and GPCC-Tri-RAHT, respectively.

In an effort to obtain unbiased results, we utilized leave-one-out cross-validation [39]. We split the input data into 48 groups ($k = 48$), using $k - 1$ groups for training and the remaining one for validation. The process is repeated a total of k times, ensuring that each group is used for validation once.

2) Evaluation Results

We trained a total of 9 classification and 13 regression models from the *scikit-learn* library for Python [25] on the partici-

TABLE 4: Performance of ML models in predicting MOS of DPC sequences in MR environments.

(a) VPCC		
Model Name	R2 Score \uparrow	MSE \downarrow
Hist Gradient Boosting Classifier	0.9590	0.0224
Bagging Classifier	0.9541	0.0251
Gradient Boosting Classifier	0.9499	0.0274
Hist Gradient Boosting Regressor	0.9472	0.0289
Logistic Regression	0.9466	0.0292
(b) GPCC-Oct-Pred		
Model Name	R2 Score \uparrow	MSE \downarrow
Random Forest Regressor	0.9298	0.0489
Bagging Regressor	0.9240	0.0529
Bagging Classifier	0.9215	0.0546
Lasso	0.9209	0.0551
ElasticNet	0.9209	0.0551
(c) GPCC-Tri-RAHT		
Model Name	R2 Score \uparrow	MSE \downarrow
Polynomial Regression (Degree 2)	0.9757	0.0214
Bagging Classifier	0.9672	0.0289
Decision Tree Classifier	0.9647	0.0312
Decision Tree Regressor	0.9647	0.0312
Hist Gradient Boosting Regressor	0.9637	0.0320

pants' ratings. The mean squared error (MSE) and the R2 (R-squared) score were used to evaluate the results. The results of the 5 best-performing models per codec are presented in Table 4.

Hist Gradient Boosting Classifier gives the best results for VPCC, but only marginally outperforms the regular Gradient Boosting Classifier and its Regressor variant. These results are in contrast with our previous analysis of ML models [22] with VPCC-encoded DPC sequences, where Gradient Boosting *Regressor* was the best performing model, with an R2 score and MSE of 0.8582 and 0.2874, respectively, and outperformed the other models by larger margins than seen here.

For GPCC-Oct-Pred, the regressor models outperformed the classifiers, with only one of the 5 best performing models belonging to the latter category. Finally, GPCC-Tri-RAHT is a mixed bag of results, with the Polynomial Regression performing the best, but closely followed by the Bagging Classifier and Decision Tree Classifier models.

Notably, the Bagging Classifier model performs well regardless of the codec. This performance can be attributed to how the Bagging Classifier splits the data and trains it using an ensemble of models, leading to smoother predictions and the final result less prone to instability [6].

FIGURE 13: Feature importance scores for input parameters per model and codec.

3) Feature Importance

Figure 13 presents feature importance for a chosen model for each codec, with a higher score indicating more importance when predicting the MOS. Since the *scikit-learn* library does not support feature importance for every model, we analyzed the best-performing model for each codec with the feature importance available: *Gradient Boosting Classifier* for VPCC, *Random Forest Regressor* for GPCC-Oct-Pred, and *Decision Tree Classifier* for GPCC-Tri-RAHT.

With a score of 0.56, the bitrate plays the most crucial role for predicting QoE for VPCC by a large margin, which is again in contrast to our previous findings where bitrate was shown to have the least amount of influence on predicting the QoE (importance score of just 0.05). This can be explained by the fact that for the current tests, we did not introduce other factors such as a fixed viewing distance or a quality switch during playback. Since we let the participants move around the DPCs and examine them from various angles, we can assume that the bitrate (and the overall quality) of the DPCs have a higher impact on the participants' final ratings.

While the bitrate is again the most influential feature for GPCC-Oct-Pred, all three parameters impact the QoE fairly evenly, with QP, depth, and bitrate having importance scores of 0.28, 0.30, and 0.42, respectively. For GPCC-Tri-RAHT, however, the level of detail when encoding the point clouds impacts the QoE the most (influence score 0.64), with bitrate having the least influence (0.12).

It can be observed that the three encoding schemes do not impact the perception of the encoded DPC sequences in the same way, and different parameters need to be considered when utilizing these codecs for DPC transmission with the aim of maximizing QoE.

B. P.1203 MODEL

The P.1203 Model by ITU-T [27] can predict the QoE of traditional (2D) videos using its various modes. Mode 0 is the most basic as it only considers the video's metadata (*i.e.*, bitrate, frame rate, and resolution) as factors to predict the QoE. In previous work [21], we fine-tuned the P.1203 mode 0 using the data from our first subjective study [23]. We expand on this work and re-trained the P.1203 model again, using the

TABLE 5: Performance of base (untuned) and fine-tuned P.1203 models for various training and validation sets. Lower RMSE and higher PLCC and SRCC are better.

	Training			Validation		
	RMSE ↓	PLCC ↑	SRCC ↑	RMSE ↓	PLCC ↑	SRCC ↑
ITU-T P.1203 Base Model	0.887	0.785	0.766	1.032	0.829	0.918
Fine-tuned on First Dataset [21]	0.813	0.953	0.919	0.955	0.828	0.958
Both Datasets						
Base Model	2.005	0.904	0.847	2.132	0.854	0.742
Fine-tuned (SHGO)	0.788	0.912	0.912	0.831	0.809	0.853
Fine-tuned (Dual Annealing)	0.787	0.912	0.922	0.836	0.809	0.854
ComPEQ-MR Dataset						
Base Model	1.994	0.911	0.904	1.922	0.935	0.892
Fine-tuned (SHGO)	0.714	0.988	0.948	0.673	0.988	0.983
Fine-tuned (Dual Annealing)	0.744	0.997	0.923	0.691	0.985	0.961
Fine-tuned (Brute Force)	0.714	0.985	0.984	0.674	0.988	0.983

data from our second round of subjective testing [24] and a combination of the two datasets to potentially obtain a more versatile model.

1) Methodology

Along with a brute force approach, we employed the simplicial homology global optimization [9] and the dual annealing (a modified version of simulated annealing [41] available in *scipy*⁹) algorithms to search for the combination of mode 0 coefficients that lead to the lowest RMSE.

The data was split into training and validation sets for each case based on the DPC objects. For the first dataset, the *LongDress* and *Loot* objects were used for training, whereas the *RedandBlack* and *Soldier* objects were used for validation. Similarly, the ComPEQ-MR dataset was also split into

⁹<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/index.html>. Accessed 27 August 2025.

(a) For both datasets.

(b) For only the ComPEQ-MR dataset.

FIGURE 14: Perceived MOS vs. predicted MOS using the untuned (base) and our fine-tuned ITU-T P.1203 models.

pairs of *BlueSpin* and *CasualSquat* for training and *Ready-ForWinter* and *FlowerDance* for validation. Notably, we only considered VPCC-encoded objects from the ComPEQ-MR dataset to have comparable results with our first study, which only used VPCC as the encoder.

2) Results

Table 5 contains the fine-tuned results, with the RMSE, Pearson Linear Correlation Coefficient (PLCC), and Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient (SRCC) being presented for each case. Comparing the fine-tuned results using both datasets with the original model and our previous work, we note that the fine-tuned models achieve lower RMSE but in most cases fail to achieve higher PLCC and SRCC values. This can be attributed to the two datasets differing too much in their nature for objective models to be able to use their data together in an effective manner. We noted this in the case of the ML models in Subsection VI-A as well.

However, when fine-tuning the model using the ComPEQ-MR dataset, the new techniques lead to lower RMSE and higher correlation scores in all cases when compared to the base (untuned) model. The accuracies of the compared models are visualized in Figure 14.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Based on a subjective study of the QoE of 41 participants when presented 4 point cloud videos at 13 different quality levels in an MR setting and on the resulting ComPEQ-MR dataset, this work provided three main contributions: (i) eye-tracking data and an analysis thereof (visual attention maps, head and gaze movement); (ii) subjective quality results (rating scores), confirming that the choice of compression algorithm (VPCC, GPCC-Oct-Pred, GPCC-Tri-RAHT under investigation) and the quality level significantly impact user perception of visual quality, but also that there are scenarios where reducing the quality level (and, thus, bandwidth consumption) does not degrade QoE; and (iii) training and validation of machine learning models (classification and regression) and fine-tuned variants of the ITU-T P.1203 model to predict/estimate the QoE of compressed point cloud videos in the MR setting.

The results suggest future work on utilizing visual attention data for viewport prediction, on quality-adaptive point cloud video streaming and presentation algorithms, and on further QoE prediction models for MR experiences.

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